

Live Joking: Live Coding Algorithmic Comedy

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the intersection between comedy and live coding by introducing our project *Live Joking*. This project examines the use of programming, as a medium and process, to create humorous or sarcastic effects analogous to that of a comedy performance. As an attempt to create theatrical effects, our project explores the process of decomposing comedy, constructing a system for live performances, as well as delivering stories and ideas through programmable actions or the programming language. By experimenting with the integration between theater, humor, and programming, *Live Joking* attempted to expand the expressiveness of live coding as an art form, while also shed light on the strategies of extending live coding to other theatrical performances.

1. INTRODUCTION

Live coding is the process of real-time manipulation of code and algorithms. While traditional live coding performances focused on creating audio and visual content, alternative live coding approaches have been developed to apply live coding in choreography, poetry, and other traditional and emerging art forms.

Compared to other tools and methods for art creation, live coding possesses several features that artists often leverage when integrating it with other forms of art. First, code and programming offer a high level of flexibility for arranging elements. The code poems collected in `"/code-poetry"` website offers a salient example. Poems collected on this website, written in programming languages, are also valid programs that generate visual representations of themselves when compiled (`"code-poetry.com"`). By arranging and constructing different elements of the programming languages, the authors created code poems that fulfill both the aesthetical purpose, being a poem, and the functional purpose, being a valid program. Another feature of live coding is its ability to generate non-deterministic outcomes, from simply calling a random function to using complicated machine learning algorithms that include stochastic processes. A relatively established live-coding toolkit usually includes the use of both features. Tidal Cycles, for example, organizes all elements of music into patterns that users can manipulate, and it also includes `"sometimes"`, `"often"`, `"irand"` and other functions that produce non-deterministic outcomes (`"Tidal Cycles"`, 2024).

We discern a parallel between these features of programming and comedy performances. A skillfully crafted joke also requires an arrangement of the setting, premise, and punchline. Take the following joke from Weekend Update, Saturday Night Live as an example:

"A 99-year-old woman in Canada broke three world swimming records for her age class on the same day, until finally someone noticed she is falling in" (`"Saturday Night Live"`, 2024)

The first half of this joke, a woman breaking swimming records, conveys the premise to the audience. The latter half of it, which serves as the punchline, is an unexpected twist. This structure, designed arrangement of premise and punchline, underpins the humor of this joke. If we reverse its structure, this joke will become the following,

“Before someone noticed that A 99-year-old woman in Canada had fallen in a swimming pool, the woman had broken three world swimming records for her age class in the same day.”

Even though it conveys a similar meaning, the jocular effect is absent. This corresponds to programming’s feature of providing flexible arrangements. Similar to the code poetics, it may be possible to arrange elements in programming in a particular manner that offers both functionality and humor. The unexpected twists that are widely adopted in comedy performances also parallel the ability of programming to produce non-deterministic outcomes. By incorporating randomness into live coding performances, unexpected results can be produced, potentially leading to laughter-evoking effects.

Based on the parallels discussed above, we designed two parts in the project *Live Joking* as endeavors to explore the possible intersections between comedy and live coding. The first part, Dark Humor, loosely adapts the form of a roast battle. By invoking drastic irony, it tries to deliver a digitized form of sarcasm originating from silent comedies. The second part, Improvisational Theater, builds from audiences’ suggested improvisation in sketch comedies and attempts to represent traditional games in comedies via programming, incorporating various unexpected components in the performances. The following two sections will introduce these two parts in detail.

2. PART ONE. DARK HUMOR

2.1 INSPIRATIONS AND FRAMEWORKS

The first part of *Live Joking*, Dark Humor, loosely took the form of a roasting battle, which includes two or two groups of comedians roasting each other. In this part of the performance, we created two characters, “The Machine” and “The Human”, and the performance presents a roasting between them.

The foundation of this part of the performance lies in the drastic irony we designed. The character “The Machine”, live-coded by a human performer, is intended to persuade “The Human” to learn programming. “The Human”, played by another actor, is a person who lost the ability to think like a real human being and can only think in terms of machine logic, where he answers all the questions proposed by “The Machine” with programming compulsively. A drastic irony was established when the audiences, who can think as real humans, watching “The Human” trying to answer simple questions using a redundant and spuriously superior machine logic. This contrast constructs an absurdity that underpins the dark humor.

2.2 PROCESS

“The Machine” is a program prewritten in p5.js that is capable of showing emotion and saying lines with a synthetic voice generated by p5.speech. During the performance, the program is live coded by a performer in the browser console. “The Human”, played by a human actor, uses Python and Python IDLE to demonstrate his thinking process via programming, and all the code is visible to the audiences on a projected screen. Python IDLE is chosen deliberately for its basic and primitive look, which fits well with the compulsive use of machine logic – reluctant and spuriously superior.

Figure 1. The Setup. Photo © Melody Loveless, 2021.

2.3 THE ROLE OF CODING

Python is well known for its readability and thus is used as a medium for storytelling in the performance. By showing code and coding process to the audiences, the thinking process and emotional changes of “The Human” is revealed. For example, when The Machine asks The Human “How old are you?”, “The Human” ’s performance will be as follows:

```
Step 1. Assigning variables in the Python script myMind.py.  
birthYear = 2001  
currentYear = 2023  
  
Step 2. Run this script in python IDLE and show audience the variables.  
>>> birthYear  
2001  
>>> currentYear  
2023  
>>> say("My age is",birthYear-currentYear)  
>>> # <say> is a predefined function in myMind.py  
Say I'm 23.  
  
Step 3. Act accordingly. The "Human" will say "I'm 23".
```

Figure 2. The Procedure of “The Human” performing an action.

Live coding plays a role in showing absurdity by depicting the mechanical and reluctant thinking process of the human, creating a contrast between the audience’s ‘human’ way of thinking and the actor’s ‘machine’ way of thinking. We also utilized error messages in Python IDLE to deliver stories. In the culminating scene of the performance, “The Human” started to realize how his way of thinking infringed on himself, constantly called the variable “myDream” which is undefined. The error message “myDream’ is undefined” was repetitively shown on the screen, conveying the strong frustration of the character is experiencing.

```

>>> myname
'Quristoff'
>>> myBirthYear
2001
>>> checkGreeted()
Someone greets you? yes
say Hi
>>> myJob
True
>>> myMoney
True
>>> myDream
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "<pyshell#5>", line 1, in <module>
    myDream
NameError: name 'myDream' is not defined
>>> myDream
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "<pyshell#6>", line 1, in <module>

```

```

myMoney = True
myName = "Quristoff"
myBirthYear = 2001

print("In My Mind-----")

```

Figure 3. 'myDream' is undefined.

3. PART TWO. IMPROVISATIONAL THEATER

3.1 FRAMEWORKS

This part of Live Joking builds from the unexpectedness and the audience suggested improvisation. In the article “Hacking Choreography: Dance and Live Coding”, the author Kate Sicchio (2014) stated that “...live programmers often use systems in advance as their starting point”. In her project, Kate Sicchio decomposed choreography into units and developed a system to align these units in an algorithmic manner (ibid.). In this part of Live Joking, we attempted to decompose comedy and construct a system for live performances that includes various kinds of unexpectedness, along with possessing the functionality that inviting audiences to create unexpectedness by themselves.

There are different ways a comedy performance can incorporate unexpected elements. In one form of audiences-suggested improvisational comedy, the actors ask audiences to write sentences on pieces of paper and scatter these pieces on the stage. After the actors start to improvise a sketch, they will pick up pieces of paper on the stage and read out the sentence written on them, which will become their line. In this setup, the actors' lines interfere with the actors' performance, creating unexpected and laughter-evoking effects. Another form of comedy includes playing unexpected sound effects where the actors need to twist the plot to rationalize them, where the sound acts as the interference of the actor's performances. Various elements in a theatrical performance, emotion, action, plots, and objects, can become interferences. By decomposing comedy into classes and elements, we constructed a system that allows the improvisation of live-coded comedies.

3.2 PROCESS

Using p5.js, we constructed a system which is capable for performers to improvise during the performance. Elements are classified into five groups: lines, emotions, behaviors, sound effects, and objects. We then conceived a list of functions.

Figure 4. The System Breakdown. The function `responseBy(prompt, method)` uses text generation algorithm. The method variable can take either “markov”, the Markov text generation implemented by Rita.js, or “gpt”, which is the GPT-2 Text generation implemented by Runway ML.

By using the system, our character can be created and manipulated in an algorithmic manner. A character possesses a name, a line, a behavior, a face, and a unique voice. The following is a snippet of code used to control the character:

```

// Creating a new character called "Friend"
let friend = new character("Friend");
greet();
cry();
friend.display();
  
```


Figure 5. An example of the character display

Our final performance was improvisational, interactive, and volatile. We asked audiences to input line, used machine to shuffle and select random elements, presenting an unexpected and absurd performance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Through the project *Live Joking*, we attempts to explore the intersection of live coding and comedy performances. Live coding possesses a high level of flexibility in arranging elements, which may allow performers to construct the structures of jokes adeptly. Programming’s ability to create non-deterministic outcomes may be utilized in creating unexpected effects, the underlying rationale for

various laughter-evoking jokes and performances. Our project comprises two parts – Dark Humor and Improvisational Theater, where each part explores integrating live joking with comedy in a certain way. Part one Dark Humor, by applying code as a medium for storytelling, presents a digitized sarcasm that is loosely based on roast battles and silent comedies. Part two Improvisation Theater, inspired by audience-suggested improvisation, leverages the process of decomposing performances and building systems to enable a high level of flexibility when live programmers perform in real-time. By decomposing theatrical performances and investigating creative use of programming, our work sheds light on the dynamic potential of live coding in the realm of comedy, offering a perspective for investigating and developing the its interdisciplinary nature.

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